

Round Robin Test for the comparison of spectral emittance measurement apparatuses

E. Le Baron, O. Raccurt, P. Giraud, M. Adier, J. Barriga, B. Diaz, P. Echegut, D. De Sousa Meneses, C. Capiani, D. Sciti, A. Soum-Glaude, C. Escape, I. Jerman, G.A. Lopez, T. Echaniz, M.J. Tello, F. Matino, A. Maccari, L. Mercatelli, E. Sani

Abstract

CSP (Concentrated Solar Power) plants technologies use the concentration of solar energy on a receiver to produce heat and then electricity by a thermodynamical process. A solar absorber material is used to convert the energy carried by light into heat. This type of material works at high temperatures (up to 1000 °C) under a highly concentrated solar flux (up to x1000 or more). Optical properties determine the performance of absorbers and it is thus necessary to measure their spectral absorptance and emittance. Solar absorptance is directly linked to the capacity of the absorber material to convert the solar flux into heat. Emittance drives the radiative thermal losses for the heated absorber and depends on the absorber temperature. The characterization of a material in operational conditions at high temperatures requires advanced apparatuses, and different measurement methods exist for the characterization of these two quantities of relevance regarding an absorber. A Round Robin Test (RRT) was conducted with the objective of comparing different new optical apparatuses and methods for measuring the emittance or luminance of various solar absorbers in air. Measurements were carried out directly at temperatures up to 560 °C while heating the samples, and also indirectly by hemispherical reflectance measurements at room temperature. In this paper, the Round Robin Test procedure to compare apparatuses is described, as well as the corresponding reflectance and emittance results on four types of materials. In addition, a discussion of some factors of influence over high temperature measurements in air and of the observed discrepancies among results from the evaluators is presented. The reliability of reflectance/emittance measurements is also demonstrated and statistics of deviations from the mean value are analyzed. These allow us to infer information about measurement reproducibility. The reflectance spectra of all samples after high temperature measurements in air (up to 500 °C) do not show any significant changes.

1 Introduction

Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) technologies concentrate solar radiation by means of mirrors onto an absorber where it is collected and converted to thermal energy. Absorbers undergo strong operational constraints and the degradation of their optical properties (such as emittance) has a direct impact on the overall performance of CSP systems. The current trend is to make the absorber operate in air and at high temperatures up to more than 1000 °C to improve the overall efficiency of the plant. In this context, development of optical devices to measure the thermo-radiative properties of materials at working temperatures has been conducted by different laboratories [1–10]. Specific requirements have been listed for CSP applications to perform measurements in operating conditions [3,7,9,10]. Most laboratories have developed methods for emissivity measurements within vacuum chambers [1–3] since most of the installed parabolic troughs operate in vacuum. Only few of them were developed to function in air and at ambient pressure [5–7]. Systems like [1] are made for measurements on refractory materials at very high temperatures in controlled atmospheres, with a CO₂ laser that heats the entire volume of the sample if the material is partially transparent. Different methods exist for the characterization of a surface emittance, being the optical methods rather than thermodynamic methods the ones are those used in this work. The first method is the inference of the emittance through the room's temperature hemispherical reflectance measurement, based on Kirchhoff's law of radiation ($\epsilon=1-R-T$) and the energy conservation laws. The second method is the direct measurement of the emittance at working temperatures by measuring the radiation

of the sample with a Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectrophotometer, which is then compared to a black body spectrum in order to obtain the spectral directional emittance. The calculation of the total normal emittance is an integration of the spectral emittance over the whole spectrum, hence, small errors in the measurement may lead to major discrepancies in the final results, and therefore the radiance measurement requires high precision. This precision is insured by using a calibrated black body measured in the exact same conditions as the sample to be used for the calibration of the measurement apparatus.

Nomenclature		temperature	
RRT	Round Robin Test	T	temperature in K
\bar{x}	arithmetic mean	$S(\lambda, T)$	signal measured by the spectrometer detector
s	standard deviation	$L(\lambda, T)$	actual luminance of a surface, which is a physical quantity of the system ($\text{W m}^{-2}\text{sr}^{-1}$)
δ_{ij}	deviation from the mean value of the specimen i for the evaluator j	$B_{\lambda}(\lambda, T)$	theoretical luminance of a perfect blackbody, as given by Planck's law ($\text{W m}^{-2}\text{sr}^{-1}$)
$\bar{\mu}$	arithmetic mean of the deviations of the evaluator j	$\rho(\lambda, T)$	spectral reflectance at temperature T
σ_j	corrected sample standard deviation of the deviations got from the evaluator j	$\tau(\lambda, T)$	spectral transmittance at temperature T
λ	wavelength	$\alpha(\lambda, T)$	spectral absorptance at temperature T
$\rho_{\text{h}}(\lambda, T_{\text{a}})$	hemispherical reflectance measurement at ambient	$\xi(\lambda, T)$	spectral emittance at temperature T
		$\xi(T)$	total emittance at T

This last type of measurement is not common. Indeed, few laboratories perform it. They have developed their own specific apparatuses for this end, leading to a great variety of systems such as [1–10]. In order to compare the performance of each of these apparatuses, to confront their measurements to the results of the room temperature method, and to determine their precision, a Round Robin Test (RRT) was established.

As developed in [11] chapter 3.4.3: “The terms “emissivity” and “emittance” are generally used interchangeably, as if they were synonymous. According to the National Bureau of Standards, the ending “-ivity” expresses the property of a material in general, for a homogeneous and semi-infinite sample i.e. an intrinsic material property (resistivity, thermal conductivity, etc.). The ending “-ance” expresses the property of a particular sample of material or a particular surface. In this case, the value depends on the specific conditions of the material (dirt, oxidation, grating, etc.) or even the thickness of the sample, i.e. strength or electrical conductance. Therefore, when talking about optical properties of materials used in solar applications (reflectance, transmittance, absorptance and emittance) the ending “-ance” shall be used, because such materials can be degraded by the thermal process, soiling, mechanical damage, etc.” and in [12] in chapter 3: “The National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST, formerly NBS) has recommended to reserve the ending “-ivity” for radiative properties of pure, perfectly smooth materials (the ones discussed in the previous chapter), and “-ance” for rough and contaminated surfaces”.

2 Round Robin Test organization

2.1 Principle

This RRT was conducted in the framework of FP8 European project STAGE-STE [13]. This RRT is carried out by CEA, in partnership with Archimede Solar Energy, the Slovenian National Institute of Chemistry, CNR-ISTEC, IK4-TEKNIKER, PROMES-CNRS laboratory, CEMHTI-CNRS laboratory, CNR-INO and the University of the Basque Country. The group is composed of two categories of participants: suppliers and laboratories. The former are suppliers of samples, active in the solar absorbers market; the latter are scientists, highly experienced in optical measurements, working in research institutes. The principle of this RRT is shown in Fig. 1. In order to ensure that the measurements made are comparable, it has been chosen to conduct a parallel RRT, meaning that each evaluator has its own sample. Indeed, a major issue for these comparative tests is that being at high temperature and in contact with air may cause samples to be oxidized. To limit this risk and highlight if any degradation occurred during the high temperature tests, hemispherical reflectance spectra were measured by all the

seven evaluators at ambient before and after heating their samples. The comparison of results from CEA and the other evaluators before and after heating is a criterion to validate the integrity of materials during the RRT. It is a key point for the comparison of all data from evaluators.

Fig 1. Procedure followed in the RRT

2.2. Samples

Three suppliers produced four types of samples with various substrates and different absorption and emittance properties. Their main characteristics are shown in Table 1. There are 13 samples in each batch 1, 2 and 3 (samples of type 1, 2 and 3) and 23 samples in batch N°4 (sample type 4).

Table 1. List of the samples used in the RRT and their properties

Supplier	Sample N°	Substrate	Surface coating	Thickness	T° max Stability in air	Emittance estimated at room Temperature	Photo
1	1	Ceramic	No	3 mm	650 °C	~ 0.8	
2	2	Stainless steel	Paint	2 mm	450 °C	> 0.9	
2	3	Stainless steel	Multi layer coating	2 mm	450 °C	< 0.3	
3	4	Stainless steel	Multi layer coating	2 mm	450 °C	< 0.1	

2.3. Optical characterization

Each supplier sent a set of identical samples from the same batch to the RRT coordinator (CEA) who finally collected samples of four different types of solar absorbers. As the measurement is made in contact with air, the samples may oxidize during the measurement. For this reason, the maximum measurement temperature has been limited in the thermal stability range indicated by the supplier (Table 1).

The seven evaluators have different apparatuses, heating controller, mechanical and optical devices and equipment systems. Fig. 1 introduces the procedure followed in the RRT. The sample homogeneity was initially checked at CEA (step #1 in Fig. 1) by measuring the hemispherical reflectance at room temperature close to the center of each sample. Different samples of the same batch were then sent in parallel to the seven evaluators to perform reflectance measurements at room temperature (step #2 in Fig. 1), in order to assess the initial properties of the samples of each evaluator. Five evaluators also have the equipment to perform emittance measurements as a function of temperature on heated samples (step #3 in Fig. 1). Next, these five evaluators performed again reflectance measurements at room temperature (step #4 in Fig. 1) after the heating to check that the sample was not degraded during the measurement at high temperatures. Finally, all the samples were sent back to the coordinator (CEA) to measure their hemispherical reflectance at room temperature and check again their thermal stability (step #5 in Fig. 1).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Step # 1: homogeneity check

First, samples were received by CEA. The verification of the samples homogeneity at CEA (step #1) is primary to ensure that the initial measurements made by each evaluator in step #2 are comparable. The homogeneity control was based on the measurement of hemispherical reflectance at room temperature and calculation of the corresponding emittance.

The CEA apparatuses for the hemispherical reflectance of the sample at room temperature consist of two spectrophotometers allowing to collect spectra from 0.28 μm to 16 μm . Spectra in the 2–16 μm range were measured using an IR Tensor 27 or a Vertex 70 FTIR made by Bruker (limited to 16 μm by the calibration wavelength range). For large samples, a diffuse gold-coated integrating sphere of 150mm with a port size of 40mm in diameter and an incidence angle of 8° was positioned at the entrance of the Tensor 27 spectrophotometer. Similarly, for small samples, a diffuse gold-coated integrating sphere of 50mm with a port size of 20mm in diameter and an incidence angle of 12° was placed at the entrance of the Vertex 70 FTIR spectrophotometer.

Spectra in the 0.28–2.5 μm range were instead collected using a Perkin Elmer Lambda 950 (NIR, visible and UV range) equipped with a Spectralon® integrating sphere of 150 mm, with a port size of 30mm in diameter. It was used for measurements from 0.28 μm to 2.5 μm with a 5 nm step and an incidence angle of 8°.

The joined spectra (see Fig. 1 of the Supplementary data), were used for the calculation of the sample emissivity according to Eqs. (1) and (2). At room temperature, the measurement method is well established and is based on a conservation of energy for opaque materials like absorbers, for which every incoming radiation is either reflected or absorbed. That is to say that at each wavelength λ , the reflectance $\rho(\lambda, T)$ and the absorptance $\alpha(\lambda, T)$ fulfil the following Kirchhoff's law:

$$\varepsilon(\lambda, T) = \alpha(\lambda, T) = 1 - \rho(\lambda, T) \quad (1)$$

However the second part of expression (1) holds true if the material is opaque ($\tau(\lambda, T) = 0$) and does not have a semitransparency domain in the measured spectral range, while the ceramic type 1 samples are partly transparent (see Fig. 1 of the Supplementary data), especially in the infrared wavelength range. Spectral emittance calculation based on hemispherical reflectance measurements alone is not sufficient for ceramic type 1 samples, a transmittance spectra is needed.

Absorptance, transmittance and emittance are inferred from reflectance measurements. Emittance $\varepsilon(T)$ was calculated in comparison to the black body spectrum $B(\lambda, T)$ at

temperature T (respectively 100 °C, 300 °C and 440 °C) on the entire spectral range (limits depend on the equipment: $\lambda_1 = 0.28 \mu\text{m}$ and $\lambda_2 = 16 \mu\text{m}$ for CEA spectrophotometers).

For opaque materials, the emittance at temperature T is usually calculated from hemispherical spectral reflectance $\rho_h(\lambda, T_a)$ spectra measured at room temperature T_a using Eq. (2).

$$\varepsilon(T) = 1 - \frac{\int_{\lambda_1}^{\lambda_2} \rho_h(\lambda, T_a) \times B(\lambda, T) d\lambda}{\int_{\lambda_1}^{\lambda_2} B(\lambda, T) d\lambda} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 2 in Supplementary data shows the emittance value calculated using Eq. (2) at 440 °C for all samples of each type from hemispherical reflectivity measurements (step #1). Table 2 shows the values of mean and standard deviation of emittance at 440 °C of all samples. In a previous RRT on the reliability of solar reflector optical performance [14], the robust statistical analysis of the results was carried out according to ISO13528:2015 standard [15]. This kind of robust statistical analysis is indeed proficient in discerning whether the experimental data is robust and furthermore it is able to eliminate extreme or non-representative values compared to the set of data. The same approach was thus applied in the present work. The analysis for each kind of samples below is based on a standard distribution of data. x^* is the median value of the data and must be equal to the mean value in the case of a normal distribution (Eq. (3)). The parameter s^* is equal to the standard deviation of a normal distribution related to x^* (Eq. (4)). We used the method A of the ISO13528:2015 [15] to calculate the convergence value of x^* and s^* .

Table 2. Emittance value at 440 °C (mean \bar{x} and standard deviation s) calculated from hemispherical measurement on all samples (step #1).

ε at 440 °C	Sample type 1	Sample type 2	Sample type 3	Sample type 4
Mean \bar{x}	0.85	0.921	0.33	0.084
Standard deviation s	0.01	0.002	0.01	0.009

$$x^* = \text{median of } x_i \text{ (} i = 1, 2, \dots, n \text{)} \quad (3)$$

$$s^* = 1.483 \text{ median of } |x_i - x^*| \text{ with } (i = 1, 2, \dots, n) \quad (4)$$

In this context, the calculated values are $\delta_{i,j}$ and μ_j . $\delta_{i,j}$ is the deviation of the values from the mean and it is also recommended to finally identify the values that deviate too much

$$\delta_{i,j} = x_{i,j} - \bar{x}_i \quad (5)$$

from the average (Eq. (5)).

With i the index on the samples and j the index on the evaluators. In the present case of test's step # 1, the calculation of this value will allow us to see the dispersion of the values with respect to the average for each series of samples.

The μ_j value on the other hand was useful to verify that the distribution follows a normal distribution for each evaluator j (Eq. (6)). If the value μ_j is not equal to 0, then the distribution is not normal.

$$\mu_j = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^n \delta_{i,j} \quad (6)$$

Another parameter σ_j is defined by formula (7).

Generally, $\mu_j > \sigma_j$ (or $\mu_j < \sigma_j$) means that the reference used for the spectrophotometry measurements is probably over (or under) estimated. Robust analysis consists in considering a law of distribution and comparing the data to this law in order to check the

$$\sigma_j = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (\delta_{i,j} - \mu_j)^2} \quad (7)$$

robustness of the hypothesis. For the following case, we assume a normal distribution law in accordance to the recommendation of standard ISO13528:2015 [15] also advocates. A plot of a normal distribution for each sample is performed from the measured parameters (see Fig. 3 in Supplementary data). Tables 3, 4 give the values obtained compared to the mean and standard deviation values calculated from the experimental data.

Table 3. Comparison of the mean and standard deviation values of all samples types calculated from the experimental data and the averages and robust deviation calculated with method A of ISO13528: 2015 [15].

ϵ at 440 °C	Sample type 1	Sample type 2	Sample type 3	Sample type 4
\bar{x}	0.846	0.921	0.33	0.084
s	0.010	0.002	0.01	0.009
x^*	0.849	0.921	0.33	0.084
s^*	0.006	0.001	0.01	0.009
$ \bar{x} - x^* $	0.003	within errors	within errors	within errors
$ s - s^* $	0.004	within errors	within errors	within errors

Table 4. Comparison of the mean values and standard deviations calculated from the experimental data after selecting the best samples, and the averages and robust deviation calculated with method A of ISO13528: 2015 [15].

ϵ at 440 °C	Sample type 1	Sample type 2	Sample type 3	Sample type 4
\bar{x}	0.851	0.921	0.335	0.09
s	0.004	0.002	0.007	0.01
x^*	0.852	0.921	0.336	0.09
s^*	0.003	0.001	0.007	0.01
$ \bar{x} - x^* $	0.001	0.001	0.001	within errors
$ s - s^* $	0.002	0.001	within errors	within errors

The batches of samples received from the suppliers contained more samples than necessary for the RRT, allowing us to select samples for the next step with the least deviation of emissivity at 440 °C. Fig. 4 in Supplementary data shows the hemispherical reflectance spectra from the selected samples for each type. Table 4 concerns only the selected samples.

By comparing Tables 3, 4, it can be seen that at 440 °C the deviation from the robust average is high for type 1 samples before selection and that the selection made it possible to reduce this difference to a low value close to the other series of samples and less than 0.001. The deviation from the robust standard was also reduced for the Type 1 sample and remained also around 0.001 which is a very acceptable value. Usually, the criterion used is that of a variability lower than the third decimal, corresponding to 0.1%. For the other types of samples the difference was not really significant and is less than the third decimal corresponding to 0.1% for both the robust average and the robust standard deviation. Fig. 2 gives the representations of $\delta_{i,j}$ for the emittance at 440 °C before (a) and after (b) the selection of the samples. It can be seen that the selection allowed us to include all the samples with $\delta_{i,j}$ between -0.01 and 0.01 except for the type 4 whose dispersion was more important. For type 4, we observed a drift with respect to the average value of the samples as a whole before selection, that could be due to either the measurement itself (drift of equipment with time) or to a non-homogeneity of the

samples. Fig. 3 gives the average values μ_j and the associated deviation $\delta_{i,j}$ (error bar) before and after the selection of homogeneous samples.

Figure 2. Representation of $\delta_{i,j}$ before (a) and after (b) selection of the calculated emittance value at 440 °C calculated from the hemispherical reflectance spectra (step # 1) for each sample and standard deviation of ± 0.01 (black dotted line).

In Fig. 3b, the average of the dispersion is done on 7 samples of each type by CEA apparatus selected for the step #2. The selection made possible to reduce all μ_j values to almost zero. All the associated standard deviations were reduced to a value less than except for Type 4. This reflects the drift observed in the measurement (see Fig. 2).

Figure 3. Representation of $\mu_j \pm \delta_{i,j}$ before (a) and after (b) selection of the calculated emittance value at 440 °C calculated from hemispherical reflectance spectra (step # 1).

3.2. Step # 2: hemispherical reflectance measurement at room temperature by evaluators

The preliminary measurements carried out at CEA (step #1) ensured low dispersion of the selected samples from the same batch had. Each evaluator then received a different sample of each type to be measured. The wavelength ranges are different for each evaluator and are summarized in Table 1 in Supplementary data. The samples were measured by the seven evaluators at room temperature before heating measurements (hemispherical reflectance measurements of evaluators are compared in Fig. 5 in Supplementary data). The multiple reflectance measurements carried out by the evaluators (minimal two measurements per sample) make it possible to confirm the reproducibility of the measurements on the same apparatus. Important variations indeed may occur depending on the equipment, the certified reference (diffuse or specular) and sample homogeneity.

In Fig. 5 of Supplementary data, we observe a very wide dispersion of results coming from different evaluators. For the sake of clarity, values from evaluator #9 were not taken into account on sample type 3. Indeed, after the measurement campaign, a diagnostic of the spectrophotometer of this evaluator showed a defect on the light source. The emittance at 100 °C, 300 °C and 440 °C of each evaluator was calculated by CEA from Kirchhoff's law considering the hemispherical reflectance spectra in the common wavelength range 1.5–16 μm for all evaluators (see Table 2 in Supplementary data). The robust analysis of these emittances at 100 °C, 300 °C and 440 °C of all evaluators gives us the values reported in Table 5.

The difference $[\bar{x}-x^*]$ of the emittance at 100 °C, 300 °C and 440 °C is less than 1% for the sample types 1, 2 and 4; and slightly above 1% (1.73%) for the type 3 (due to one evaluator erroneous values). This shows that here again the data set is well representative of a normal Gaussian law and justifies the statistical calculations. Moreover, the average deviation is more important between the evaluators in step #2 than for CEA in step #1. Indeed, if we compare these values to those calculated in step #1 (Table 4), we note that the difference between evaluators was much greater than the variation observed for a single evaluator on all samples. For instance, type 2 sample at 440 °C presented a deviation s from the mean value of 0.002 for CEA (Table 4) and 0.03 (Table 5) for the evaluators. This suggests that this variation is due to the dispersion of the measurements from one laboratory to another and not to the variations of the samples in the batch. It was observed that there were no remarkable differences (less than ± 0.01) between the emittance calculated in the common and in the full wavelength ranges (see Fig. 6 in supplementary data). Regarding the influence of temperature (in the 100–440 °C range), the mean emittance values of type 3 and type 4 samples slightly increase with temperature from +0.03 to +0.06.

Table 5. Robust analysis of calculated emittance at 100 °C, 300 and 440 °C between 1.5 and 16 μm (common range) from the hemispherical reflectance measurements of each laboratory.

$\epsilon@ 100\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$	Sample type 1	Sample type 2	Sample type 3	Sample type 4
\bar{x}	0.87	0.91	0.23	0.05
s	0.03	0.03	0.06	0.02
x^*	0.88	0.92	0.25	0.05
s^*	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.01
$ \bar{x} - x^* $	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.00
$ s - s^* $	0.02	0.02	0.04	0.01

$\epsilon@300\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$	Sample type 1	Sample type 2	Sample type 3	Sample type 4
\bar{x}	0.85	0.91	0.27	0.06
s	0.03	0.03	0.06	0.02
x^*	0.86	0.92	0.29	0.06
s^*	0.02	0.01	0.03	0.01
$ \bar{x} - x^* $	0.01	0.01	0.02	within errors
$ s - s^* $	0.01	0.02	0.03	within errors

$\epsilon@ 440\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$	Sample type 1	Sample type 2	Sample type 3	Sample type 4
\bar{x}	0.83	0.92	0.29	0.08
s	0.03	0.03	0.06	0.02
x^*	0.84	0.92	0.31	0.08
s^*	0.01	0.03	0.03	0.02
$ \bar{x} - x^* $	0.01	within errors	0.02	within errors
$ s - s^* $	0.02	within errors	0.03	within errors

Fig. 4 gives the divergence from the mean value $\bar{\delta}_{i,j}$ of the set of measurements at $\epsilon@440$ °C of each evaluator for the 4 types of samples. It can be seen that all the samples show a deviation of the values from the mean value $\bar{\delta}_{i,j}$ between -0.07 and 0.07 , except for the type 3 due to one value.

Figure 4. Representation of $\delta_{i,j}$ of the emittance value at 440 °C calculated from the hemispherical reflectance spectra (step # 2).

Fig. 5 gives the average values μ_j and the associated deviation $\delta_{i,j}$ (error bar) at 440 °C for the different evaluators. The values are close to zero, except for evaluators N°5 (red marker) and N°9 (purple marker).

Figure 5. Representation of μ_j and $\delta_{i,j}$ of the emittance value at 440 °C calculated from hemispherical reflectance spectra (step # 2).

It can be seen that all the evaluators show a value of μ_j between ± 0.03 , except for evaluator N°9.

As explained previously, the values of one evaluator on type 3 are erroneous due to defect on the light source. This explains the value $\mu_j < -0.05$ and the larger deviations (> 0.04) for this evaluator.

For the other ones, all μ_j values are around zero. The associated standard deviations are reduced to ± 0.02 .

We see in Fig. 5 that the values of μ_j are not all equal to zero. Evaluators N°2, N°6 and N°7 are extremely close to zero with a very low deviation $\delta_{i,j}$, well below 0.01. This shows that for these evaluators the measurements are close to the right value. Evaluator N°8 slightly overestimate the value (< 0.02) with a low associated error as for evaluators N°2 and N°6. Evaluators N°5, N°9 and N°10 deviate from the reference (zero) by more than 0.02 with a large error bar which shows that their measurements are scattered and far from the correct value.

3.3. Step # 3: sample emittance measurement at high temperature in spectral range 4–16 μm

The high temperature measurement of emittance has several interests. First, it is a more straightforward measurement of the thermal emittance property, at the operating temperature that cannot be deduced by calculation from room temperature measurements. Secondly, emissivity measurements allow to determine whether or not the optical properties of the material (absorptivity, reflectivity) are independent of temperature and do not change during heating. Within the framework of this RRT, five evaluators developed methods for direct thermal measurement of emittance or reflectance in different applications [1–10]. A scheme and a description of these set-up are summarized in Table 3 in Supplementary data and described in [1,2,5,6,8] respectively. All equipment setup and methods were very different in terms of heating (laser heating, furnace, electron beam, electrical resistive heater), environment (vacuum chamber, ambient air or controlled atmosphere), reference (blackbody or another material with known emittance) and temperature control (spot welded thermocouple, IR sensor). Details on wavelength range and operation temperatures are summarized in Table 4 of Supplementary data.

A detailed description of the CEA set-up is published elsewhere [6,7], and total emittance vs T was calculated as the ratio between the sample spectral radiance and that of the calibrated blackbody spectral radiance according to expression (8).

$$\varepsilon(T) \equiv \frac{\int_{\lambda_1}^{\lambda_2} L(\lambda, T) d\lambda}{\int_{\lambda_1}^{\lambda_2} B(\lambda, T) d\lambda} \quad (8)$$

The sample, heated by means of an electric system at the working temperature, is maintained in air atmosphere. An optical system alternately collects the radiation of the sample and the blackbody which is analysed by an FT-IR spectrometer. Sample temperature is measured with a thermocouple in contact with the heater resistive wire. To get the thermal emittance at T, three measurements have to be done: the sample heated to T and the blackbody at two temperatures around T (here ± 10 °C). Indeed, there is a difference between the emitted and the detected radiations due to the response function of the instrument.

These two black body measurements are used to create a calibration file, which is then applicable to any sample measurement made at a temperature between the two blackbody temperatures. This is giving us the emittance spectrum of the sample, the total emittance being the integration of the spectral emittance over the whole spectrum.

It is noteworthy that CEA's sample chamber is not free of H₂O and CO₂ gases, thus some undesirable radiations and absorption may take place.

As already mentioned, each evaluator used a different measuring equipment with its own spectral range of wavelength: the calculation of the total emittance (Eq. (9)) can therefore be done both on the total range of the instrument and on the largest spectral range common to all instruments (4–16 μm).

$$\varepsilon(T) = \frac{\int_{\lambda_1}^{\lambda_2} \varepsilon_\lambda(\lambda) B(\lambda, T) d\lambda}{\int_{\lambda_1}^{\lambda_2} B(\lambda, T) d\lambda} \quad (9)$$

The first option was selected to compare the capacities of the instruments. The second one was instead used to compare the quality of the spectral measurements and the impact of the difference in the spectrum on the emittance.

According to the European standard EN-673:2011, the integration interval is limited to 1–25 μm . Some equipment are able to measure from 1,2 to 28,5 μm . Other laboratories do not have data from 16 to 25 μm , and then the integrated part is normally from 1 to 25. This limited wavelength may affect the results but we showed in step #2 and 4 that the

difference in emittance is estimated to be less than 0.01 (see Fig. 6 in Supplementary datas except for sample type 1).

In Fig. 6, total emittance values measured at different temperatures by evaluators on the common wavelength range 4–16 μm (see Table 3 in Supplementary data) for the four sample types are compared with the emittance calculated from room temperature measurements (step #2).

Figure 6. Thermal emittance measured at different temperatures by evaluators (markers) compared with emittance calculated from hemispherical reflectance at room temperature measurements in step #1 (mean CEA dotted line) and step #2 (mean evaluators dotted line) with Eq. (2).

For type 1 samples, some evaluators showed an emittance greater than 1 at low temperature. In addition, cracks were observed above 500 °C by some evaluators on type 1 ceramic samples, very likely due to thermal shock issues. To solve this issue, a temperature limit was set at 480 °C for this sample type. Additionally, these samples have a semitransparency domain in the infrared wavelength range. The semitransparency of the materials hinders from measuring the IR properties, in particular, at elevated temperatures, due to a parasite or environment radiation, and even self-radiation of the sample, passing directly through the sample and failing to be measured [16,17,18].

For the type 2, 3 & 4 samples, the high temperature measurements highlight similar results for the two evaluators' N°6 & 7. There were no relevant differences between the emittance measured at high temperature (step #3) and the emittance calculated from room temperature reflectance (steps #1 & #2). Although, each of these evaluators doesn't have completely identical samples, as well as different equipment, these two evaluators have the same trend as the results obtained from the emittance calculated from room temperature measurements. The thermal dispersion between evaluators is presented in Figs. 7 and 8 on type 3 samples, showing that material temperature measurement is not yet mastered.

Figure 7. Comparison of the spectral emittance of type 3 samples compared for five evaluators at almost 200 °C (left) and 400 °C (right).

It can be observed in Fig. 7 that, for some evaluators, the spectral emittance decreases with temperature, whereas evaluators N°6 ,7 & 9 manage to measure an almost constant spectral emittance at any temperature ranging from 200 °C to 400 °C. For example, the temperature of the sample 3 for the evaluator N°10 was underestimated, therefore its temperature regulation was not optimal. One advantage of the evaluator N°6 apparatus is the temperature measurement directly on the surface of the sample at the edge.

Overall, the high temperature measurements highlighted the observed discrepancies due to the use of the different apparatuses, difficulty to control thermal heating and contact temperature measurement method on two of the apparatuses. The cause of this problem may be in the size, the surface roughness and the nature of the samples, especially for type 1 samples since ceramic is much less conductive than steel and the samples are thicker than the others (thickness > 2 mm). Previous works [5,7] show perfect match between calculated and measured emittance for thin steel samples (< 1 mm). The thickness of the samples increases their thermal resistance and therefore reduces their surface temperature (heating is applied on the back of the sample for obvious reasons). This phenomenon was already observed in the literature [6].

For some apparatuses, the measured temperature is the temperature of the heating resistors, or the back side of the sample and not the front side surface temperature of the sample. The variability of the measured emittance can also be due to the temperature calibration range, as well as the wavelength range to calculate the total emittance. For example, the thermal emittance may be calculated using the black body temperature closer to the sample thermal measurement or on a large range of temperatures.

3.4. Step # 4: hemispherical reflectance measurement at room temperature after heating by evaluators

The samples were measured by five evaluators at room temperature after heating in order to ensure that no degradation of the sample may occur during the high temperature measurements. The comparison with the emittance calculated before heating is shown in Fig. 8.

Figure 8. Emittance calculated from hemispherical reflectance measurements at room temperature with Eq. (2) in the common range of 1.5–16 μm (dotted curves are calculated before heating and solid curves are calculated after heating).

The full wavelength range hemispherical reflectance measurements and thermal emittance $\epsilon(T)$ calculated by each evaluator are detailed in Supplementary data. Two evaluators observed cracks in the sample type 1. It has been observed that the results were completely different after heating due to the degradation of the sample. As two evaluators observed cracks in their type 1 sample, the results were completely different after heating due to the degradation of the sample. Two evaluators (N°6 & N°7) found the same results before and after heating for all the types of materials, thus no degradation occurred on the different materials types due to high temperature measurements in their case.

For Type 2 samples, the curves of the evaluators N°6, N°7 and N°8 are almost superimposed, with a slight difference of less than 0.005 from previous values on the same sample (step #2), and less than 0.002 for the evaluators N°10. For type 4 samples, the curves of the evaluators' N°6, N°7 and N°9 are almost superimposed, with a difference of less than 0.003 from step #2 curves.

To summarise, as presented in Fig. 9 on the type 3 and type 4 samples, the results that are considered reliable are those of an evaluator that present very good match between thermal measurements at high temperature (step #3) and calculations from room temperature measurements (before #2 and after heating #4), with a similar evolution with temperature. Also, the deviation of the various measures done by this evaluator must be low. Its high temperature emissivity apparatus should have a sample chamber purged with dry air to avoid CO₂ and water absorption.

Figure 9. Sample 3 thermal emittance calculated from reflectance measurements at room temperature before (dotted line, step #2) and after heating (solid line, step #4) and from values measured on heated samples (bullets, step #3).

4. Conclusions and future work

This paper presents a Round Robin Test (RRT) lead by CEA with nine partners and seven evaluators. A comparison of different new optical apparatuses and methods for measuring the emittance of various solar absorbers in air was carried out. Firstly, direct measurements at various elevated temperatures while heating the samples (step #3), and secondly indirect measurements by hemispherical reflectance measurements at room temperature and associated emittance calculation based on Kirchhoff's law of radiation (step #2). A large range of materials and spectral properties, from high emittance bulk ceramics with transparency domain and metals covered with paints to high emittance/low emittance selective coatings was studied. The high temperature measurements were performed under atmospheric conditions between room temperature and 560 °C in the maximal spectral range 1.25–28 μm and common range 4–16 μm . The results at room temperature (step #2 & 4) showed some dispersion depending on the equipment, on the chosen certified reference (diffuse or specular) by each evaluator and the sample homogeneity in the same batch.

This Round Robin Test also showed the difficulty of correctly measuring the thermal emittance as a function of temperature. The wide dispersion of results proved the difficulty to control thermal heating and material temperature measurement of some apparatuses.

For the involved laboratories, this comparison of values/measures is very important to identify measurement problems and their origin:

- the differences between reflectance results at room temperature can be due to certified reference (diffuse or specular) amongst evaluators;
- the differences between the thermal emittance results are in some cases due to errors in the measurement/estimation of the sample temperature; or to uncertainties in the blackbody signal or temperature;
- the temperature intervals of the blackbody to perform the calibrations are also parameters analysed in the thermal emittance dispersion.

Overall, modifying the heating system has been proved to be the best solution in order to provide more consistent emittance measurements between different apparatuses.

The high temperature apparatuses developed by two of the participating evaluators gave similar results with different apparatuses. A low dispersion for both direct (step #3 by heating samples) and indirect (step #2 at room temperature) emittance assessment methods for opaque materials in the infrared range was observed.

It was shown that due to uncertainties on the surface temperature of the sample, some apparatuses are more suitable to the measurement of (thermally conductive) metallic materials than refractive materials such as ceramics. Few studies have been reported on sample surface temperature measurements methods, uncertainty and gradient across the sample thickness [2,19–23] and in the evaluation of the emittance uncertainty [24–28]. It is suggested that this work could also be the first step towards setting up a new common work dedicated to the study of solar absorbers and the measurement of their optical properties.

Acknowledgement

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Energy Research Alliance (EERA) with the European project N° 609837 “Scientific and Technological Alliance for Guaranteeing the European Excellence in Concentrating Solar Thermal Energy – STAGE STE”. This work was supported by the French "Investments for the future" program managed by the French National Research Agency under contracts ANR-10-LABX-22-01-SOLSTICE, ANR-10-EQPX-49-SOCRATE and ANR-11-EQPX-0014-DURASOL for some of the equipment. This work has also received funding from the Auvergne region.

References

- [1] D. De Sousa Meneses, P. Melin, L. del Campo, L. Cosson, P. Echegut, Apparatus for measuring the emissivity of materials from far infrared to visible wavelengths in extreme conditions of temperature, *Infrared Phys. Technol.* 69 (2015) 96–101.
- [2] L.D. Campo, R.B. Perez-Saez, X. Esquisabel, I. Fernandez, M.J. Tello, New experimental device for infrared spectral directional emissivity measurements in a controlled environment, *Rev. Sci. Instrum.* 77 (2006) 113111.
- [3] B.D. Demange, M. Bejet, B. Dufour, New methods for measuring the thermal emissivity of semi-transparent and opaque materials, *Rev. Sci. Instrum.* (2006).
- [4] J. Jyothi, A. Soum-Glaude, H.S. Nagaraj, Harish C. Barshilia, Optical properties of TiAlC/TiAlCN/TiAlSiCN/TiAlSiCO/TiAlSiO tandem absorber coatings by phasemodulated spectroscopic ellipsometry, *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cells* 171 (2017).
- [5] A. Soum-Glaude, A. Le Gal, M. Bichotte, C. Escape, L. Dubost, Optical characterization of TiAlN_x/TiAlN_y/Al₂O₃ tandem solar selective absorber coatings, *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cells* 170 (2017) 254–262.
- [6] P. Giraud, J. Brailon, C. Delord, O. Raccurt, Development of optical tools for the characterization of selective solar absorber at elevated temperature, *AIP Conf. Proc.* 1734 (2016) 130008.
- [7] P. Giraud, J. Brailon, O. Raccurt, Selective solar absorber emissivity measurement at elevated temperature, *AIP Conf. Proc.* 1850 (2016) 130004.
- [8] L. Mercatelli, M. Meucci, E. Sani, Facility for assessing spectral normal emissivity of solid materials at high temperature, *Appl. Opt.* 54 (2015).
- [9] L. Bartelmeß, et al., Characterization of high temperature solar thermal selective absorber coatings at operation temperature, *Energy Procedia* 49 (2014).
- [10] T. Echaniz, et al., Importance of the spectral emissivity measurements at working temperature to determine the efficiency of a solar selective coating, *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cells* 140 (2015).
- [11] Standard IEC TS 62862-1-1, Solar thermal electric plants - Part 1-1: Terminology, 2018.
- [12] M.F. Modest, *Radiative Heat Transfer*, 3rd edition, Academic Press, 2013.

- [13] (<http://www.stage-ste.eu/>).
- [14] M. Montecchi, C. Delord, O. Raccurt, A. Disdier, F. Sallaberry, A. García de Jalón, et al., Hemispherical reflectance results of the SolarPACES reflectance Round Robin, *Energy Proc.* 69 (2015).
- [15] ISO 13528: statistical methods for use in proficiency testing by interlaboratory comparison.
- [16] O. Rozenbaum, D. De Sousa Meneses, P. Echegut, Texture and porosity effects on the thermal radiative behavior of alumina ceramics, *Int. J. Thermophys.* 30 (2009).
- [17] B. Rousseau, J.F. Brun, D. De Sousa Meneses, P. Echegut, Temperature measurement: christiansen wavelength and blackbody reference, *Int. J. Thermophys.* 26 (2005).
- [18] G.W. Lee, S. Jeon, N.J. Yoo, C.-W. Park, S.-N. Park, S.Y. Kwon, S.-H. Lee, Normal and directional spectral emissivity measurement of semi-transparent materials using two-substrate method: alumina, *Int. J. Thermophys.* 32 (2011).
- [19] M. Honner, P. Honnerová, Survey of emissivity measurement by radiometric methods, *Appl. Opt.* 54 (2015).
- [20] L.M. Hanssen, S.N. Mekhontsev, V.B. Khromchenko, Infrared spectral emissivity characterization facility at NIST, *Proc. SPIE* 5405 (2004).
- [21] B. Wolfgang, R. Matthias, Device for spectral emissivity measurements of ceramics using a FT-IR spectrometer, *Proc. SPIE* 5532 (2004).
- [22] J.M. Dai, X.B. Wang, G.B. Yuan, Fourier transform spectrometer for spectral emissivity measurement in the temperature range between 60 and 1500 °C, *J. Phys. Conf. Ser.* 13 (2005).
- [23] M. Ryzdek, T. Stark, M. Arduini-Schuster, J. Manara, Newly designed apparatus for measuring the angular dependent surface emissivity in a wide wavelength range and at elevated temperatures up to 1400 °C, *J. Phys. Conf. Ser.* (2012).
- [24] R.B. Pérez-Sáez, L. del Campo, M.J. Tello, Analysis of the accuracy of methods for the direct measurement of emissivity, *Int. J. Thermophys.* 29 (2008).
- [25] P.C. Dufour, N.L. Rowell, A.G. Steele, Fourier-transform radiation thermometry: measurements and uncertainties, *Appl. Opt.* 37 (1998).
- [26] Y.F. Zhang, J.M. Dai, Z.W. Wang, W.D. Pan, L. Zhang, A spectral emissivity measurement facility for solar absorbing coatings, *Int. J. Thermophys.* 34 (2013).
- [27] C. Monte, J. Hollandt, The determination of the uncertainties of spectral emissivity measurements in air at the PTB, *Metrologia* 47 (2010).
- [28] R.R. Corwin, A. Rodenburgh, Temperature error in radiation thermometry caused by emissivity and reflectance measurement error, *Appl. Opt.* 33 (10) (1994).